

A MIXED FINITE ELEMENT FOR INTERLAMINAR STRESS ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES*

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a mixed finite element with 49 stress parameters and 42 displacement parameters, which is constructed on the basis of the Global-Local variational model, for solving the problem of interlaminar stress analysis in composite laminates. The bending problem of thick laminated composite plate and typical Pagano problem have been used here as illustrating examples. The numerical results have shown that the mixed finite element presented in this paper is effective for calculating the interlaminar stresses in composite laminates.

INTRODUCTION

Owing to the high specific strength and stiffness ratios, fiber reinforced composite (FRC) materials have been found its extensive applications as a kind of structural material in many engineering fields. Early stage failure caused by delamination in composite laminates, which is the most common failure mode in FRC, has been being a problem of concern. The solution of this problem must be preceded by a reliable stress analysis in which the interlaminar stress components are considered. The analysis is also important in examining damage and failure of FRC laminates.

In late 1960's Summer¹, Pipes² and their cooperators as the pioneers in the field of interlaminar stress analysis, obtained solution for a composite laminate under uniform tension load and confirmed the existence of interlaminar stresses. After that, the interlaminar stress analysis methods and the stress distribution features were investigated, and some meaningful results have been obtained. Up to data, however, most of the work in this field are confined to the analysis of the simple quasi-3D Pipes-Pagano problem and subjected to the limitation of lager number of the laminates. To remove the restrictions, this paper adopts a mixed finite element method on the basis of the Global-Local variational model to solve the problem of interlaminar stress analysis.

THEORY AND FORMULATION

1. Global-Local Variational Model and Mixed Finite Element Method.
An efficient laminate variational model, aiming at reducing the intrac-table numerical work for interlaminar stress analysis of composite laminates with large layer numbers, was proposed by Pagano and Soni³. The idea is to divide the laminates into two types of subdomain through the laminate's thickness. One is so-called local domain where stress hybrid element based on modified Reissner functional is adopted, whereas the other one is global domain discretized by high order displacement finite element. This mixed model has been successful in getting accurate stresses in the local domain and saving computer time by making use of the respective features of the two formulations. The basic formula of the

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Global-Local model is:

$$F(u, \sigma) = \int_{V_G} \tilde{w} dv + \int_{V_L} \left[\frac{1}{2} \sigma_{ij} (u_{i,j} + u_{j,i}) - w \right] dv - \int_{S'} \bar{T}_i u_i dS \quad (1)$$

where $\tilde{w} = \tilde{w}(u_i)$ is the strain energy density function in the global domain V_G , $w = w(\sigma_{ij})$ is the complementary strain energy in the local domain V_L , and \bar{T}_2 is prescribed traction at the external force boundary S' . In fact, this can be considered as an application of patched variational principle.

Identical displacement interpolation functions are used in the two regions to keep the displacement continuity at the boundary between the regions. Let

$$u^e = Nq^e \quad (2)$$

in which N is the interpolation function and q^e are nodal displacement parameters. In the local domain, the hybrid stress element is used, the stress tensor within each hybrid stress element is assumed as:

$$\sigma_e = P\beta^e \quad (3)$$

where P is the stress interpolation function which satisfies the homogeneous equilibrium condition, and β^e are the element stress parameters. Substituting Eqs. (2) and (3) into (1) and varying with respect to two sets of parameters, we can easily obtain the following generalized discrete equilibrium equation:

$$K_q = Q \quad (4)$$

in which the generalized stiffness matrix is

$$K = K_G + K_L \quad (5)$$

where K_G and K_L represent the stiffness matrices of the elements in global and local domain respectively, and are evaluated by the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} K_G &= \int_{V_G} B^T D B dV, & K_L &= \sum_e G^T H^{-1} G \\ G^e &= \int_{V_L^e} P^T B dV, & H^e &= \int_{V_L^e} P^T S P dV \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

2. Displacement Interpolation Function

In this paper, six-node isoparametric triangle interpolation function is adopted in X-O-Y plane which is parallel to the plate surface, while in the thickness direction, the displacement is discreted by Lagrange interpolation. The shape of the element is prismatic as illustrated in Fig.1. The displacement interpolation formulas are:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{Bmatrix} u \\ v \end{Bmatrix} &= \frac{1-\xi}{2} \sum_{i=1}^6 N_i(L_j) \begin{Bmatrix} u_i^a \\ v_i^a \end{Bmatrix} + \frac{1+\xi}{2} \sum_{i=1}^6 N_i(L_j) \begin{Bmatrix} u_i^b \\ v_i^b \end{Bmatrix} \\ w &= -\frac{\xi(1-\xi)}{2} \sum_{i=1}^6 N_i(L_j) w_i^a + (1-\xi^2) \sum_{i=1}^6 N_i(L_j) w_i^c + \frac{\xi(1+\xi)}{2} \sum_{i=1}^6 N_i(L_j) w_i^b \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where ξ is a normalized element transverse coordinate defined by $\xi = (Z - Z_0)/t$, Z_0 is the coordinate value of Z on the central plane of the element, and t is half thickness of the element. The superscripts a, b and c stand for the different faces as shown in Fig.1, and $L_j (j=1,2,3)$ are

the area coordinates used to construct the inplane displacement interpolation function:

$$\begin{aligned} N_i &= L_i(2L_i-1) & i=1, 2, 3 \\ N_4 &= 4L_1L_2, & N_5 = 4L_2L_3, & N_6 = 4L_1L_3 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

3. Stress Interpolation Function in Hybrid Stress Element

The stress interpolation function has to be complete polynomials about x and y in order to prevent the appearing of spurious asymmetric displacement mode⁴ and to ensure the interlaminar traction continuity so as to obtain an exact stress result⁶. Based on the above requirements, the stress field within a hybrid element takes the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_x &= \left\{ \frac{1}{2t} [\beta_{10} + (\beta_4 - \beta_{44} - \beta_{18})x + \beta_{11}y + \frac{1}{2}(\beta_5 - \beta_{45} - \beta_{20})x^2 + (\beta_6 - \beta_{46} - 2\beta_{21})xy + \beta_{12}y^2] \right\} + \frac{3}{2t^2} \xi \{ \beta_{22} + \beta_{23}x + \beta_{24}y + \beta_{25}x^2 + \beta_{26}xy + \beta_{27}y^2 \} \\ \sigma_y &= \left\{ \frac{1}{2t} [\beta_{13} + \beta_{14}x + (\beta_1 - \beta_{41} - \beta_{47})y + \beta_{15}x^2 + (\beta_2 - \beta_{42} - 2\beta_{19})xy + \frac{1}{2}(\beta_3 - \beta_{43} - \beta_{20})y^2] \right\} + \frac{3}{2t^2} \xi \{ \beta_{28} + \beta_{29}x + \beta_{30}y + \beta_{31}x^2 + \beta_{32}xy + \beta_{33}y^2 \} \\ \sigma_{xy} &= \left\{ \frac{1}{2t} [\beta_{16} + \beta_{17}x + \beta_{18}y + \beta_{19}x^2 + \beta_{20}xy + \beta_{21}y^2] \right\} + \frac{3}{2t^2} \xi \left\{ [\beta_{34} + \beta_{35}x + \beta_{36}y + \beta_{37}x^2 + \frac{1}{2}(\beta_7 - \beta_{47} - 2\beta_{25} - 2\beta_{33})xy - \frac{t}{2}(\beta_5 + \beta_{45} + \beta_3 + \beta_{43})xy + \beta_{38}y^2 + \beta_{39}x^3 + \frac{1}{4}(\beta_8 - \beta_{48})x^2y + \frac{1}{4}(\beta_9 - \beta_{49})xy^2 + \beta_{40}y^3] \right\} \\ \sigma_{yz} &= \frac{3}{4t} \left\{ [(\beta_{30} + \beta_{32}x + 2\beta_{33}y) + \frac{2t}{3}(\beta_1 + \beta_{41}) + \frac{2}{3}t(\beta_2 + \beta_{42})x + \frac{2}{3}t(\beta_3 + \beta_{43})y + \beta_{35} + \frac{1}{2}(\beta_7 - \beta_{47} - 2\beta_{25} - 2\beta_{33})y - \frac{t}{2}(\beta_5 + \beta_{45} + \beta_3 + \beta_{43})y + 3\beta_{39}x^2 + \frac{1}{2}(\beta_8 - \beta_{48})xy + \frac{1}{4}(\beta_9 - \beta_{49})y^2 + 2\beta_{37}x] \right\} + \xi \left\{ \left[\frac{\beta_{41} - \beta_1}{2} + \frac{\beta_{42} - \beta_2}{2}x + \frac{\beta_{43} - \beta_3}{2}y \right] \right\} - \xi^2 \frac{3}{4t} \left\{ [(\beta_{30} + \beta_{32}x + 2\beta_{33}y) + \beta_{35} + \frac{1}{2}(\beta_7 - \beta_{47} - 2\beta_{25} - 2\beta_{33})y - \frac{t}{2}(\beta_5 + \beta_{45} + \beta_3 + \beta_{43})y + 3\beta_{39}x^2 + \frac{1}{2}(\beta_8 - \beta_{48})xy + \frac{1}{4}(\beta_9 - \beta_{49})y^2 + 2\beta_{37}x] \right\} \\ \sigma_{xz} &= \frac{3}{4t} \left\{ [(\beta_{23} + 2\beta_{25}x + \beta_{26}y) + \frac{2t}{3}(\beta_4 + \beta_{44}) + \frac{2}{3}t(\beta_5 + \beta_{45})x + \frac{2}{3}t(\beta_6 + \beta_{46})y + \beta_{36} + \frac{1}{2}(\beta_7 - \beta_{47} - 2\beta_{25} - 2\beta_{33})x - \frac{t}{2}(\beta_5 + \beta_{45} + \beta_3 + \beta_{43})x + 2\beta_{38}y + \frac{1}{4}(\beta_8 - \beta_{48})x^2 + \frac{1}{2}(\beta_9 - \beta_{49})xy + 3\beta_{40}y^2] \right\} + \xi \left\{ \left[\frac{\beta_{44} - \beta_4}{2} + \frac{\beta_{45} - \beta_5}{2}x + \frac{\beta_{46} - \beta_6}{2}y \right] \right\} - \xi^2 \frac{3}{4t} \left\{ [(\beta_{23} + 2\beta_{25}x + \beta_{26}y) + \beta_{36} + \frac{1}{2}(\beta_7 - \beta_{47} - 2\beta_{33})x - \frac{t}{2}(\beta_5 + \beta_{45} + \beta_3 + \beta_{43})x + 2\beta_{38}y + \frac{1}{4}(\beta_8 - \beta_{48})x^2 + \frac{1}{2}(\beta_9 - \beta_{49})xy + 3\beta_{40}y^2] \right\} \\ \sigma_z &= \left\{ \left[\frac{1}{2}(\beta_7 + \beta_{47}) + \frac{1}{2}(\beta_8 + \beta_{48})x + \frac{1}{2}(\beta_9 + \beta_{49})y - \frac{t}{4}(\beta_5 - \beta_{45} + \beta_3 - \beta_{43}) \right] \right\} + \frac{3}{4} \xi \left\{ [(\beta_{47} - \beta_7) + (\beta_{48} - \beta_8)x + (\beta_{49} - \beta_9)y] + \frac{t}{4}(\beta_5 + \beta_{45} + \beta_3 + \beta_{43}) \right\} + \frac{3}{4} \xi^2 \left\{ (\beta_5 - \beta_{45} + \beta_3 - \beta_{43}) \right\} + \xi^3 \left\{ -\frac{1}{4} [(\beta_{47} - \beta_7) + (\beta_{48} - \beta_8)x + (\beta_{49} - \beta_9)y] - \frac{t}{4} [(\beta_5 + \beta_{45} + \beta_3 + \beta_{43})] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

From these equations, it is obvious that the interlaminar traction continuity can be neatly expressed as

$$\beta_k^i = \beta_{k-40}^{i+1} \quad (k=41 \text{ --- } 49)$$

In calculating element stiffness, the integration about ξ is carried out explicitly to reduce computation cost, while Gaussian quadrature technique is used to perform the integration about x and y . It is determined through numerical experiments that 13 points formula with an algebraic precision of 7 order is required for the integration of H and G matrices, whereas 9 points, 5 order quadrature formula is needed for the evaluation of the displacement element stiffness matrix.

4. Discussion on Element Quality

The necessary condition ensuring a hybrid stress element stiffness matrix to possess correct rank is $n_b \geq n_q - 1$, where 1 is the rigid body displacement degrees of freedom, n_q and n_b are the numbers of the displacement and stress parameters of the element respectively. In the present paper, $n_b = 49$, $n_q = 42$, $l = 6$. It is obvious that this condition is satisfied. In addition, the spectral analysis and patch test for examining the quality of element stiffness matrix are performed and have shown that the mixed finite element meets all the requirements for the computational accuracy and convergence.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

Two representative examples are chosen in this section to examine the feasibility of the method as well as the formulation proposed in this paper.

1. Cylindrical Bending of Thick Laminated Composite Plate

Consider a [0/90/0] laminate cylindrical bending problem as shown in Fig.2. The laminate is subjected to sineous distributed load on the upper surface and simply supported at $x=0$ and $x=1$ edges. The laminar material properties used are the same as those in reference 5.

The convergence of the deflection at the center of a plate with a ratio of thickness to span of $h/l=0.1$ is examined by separately using hybrid stress element and high order displacement element. The results are shown in Fig.3, in which the vertical ordinate represents the deviation from the exact solution by Ref. 5. It can be seen that the solution for both kinds of elements converge to exact solution as the meshes become fine, but from different directions.

2. Pagano Problem

The typical Pagano problem of a [0/90/90/0] symmetric laminate is solved by the Global-Local finite element method in this paper. The material constants adopted are those in Ref.7, and four hybrid stress element division is used for the half laminate thickness. Fig.4 shows the distribution of interlaminar stress σ_2 at interface of $Z=0$. The dotted line is the finite element results by Ref.6. This diagram proves that by using the stress element formulation in this paper, a stress solution with good accuracy can be obtained.

The dotted line in Fig.5 and Fig.6 are the stress σ_2 distributions at $Z=0$ and $Z=h$. (0 and 90 interface) by mixed finite element method. This time, the half thickness is discretized by two stress elements in the inner part of the laminate (local domain) and two displacement element in its outer part (two global domains). The solid lines are results obtained by displacement finite element proposed by this paper using the same mesh in Fig.4, which are used to compare them with the results of the Global-Local mesh division. In Fig.5, a certain extent of deviation

exists between the two curves; however, good agreement can be seen between those in Fig.6. This fact suggests that satisfactory stress result in local domain can be acquired by using mixed finite element method although the stresses in the remaining part may be less accurate. The main advantage of the present method is that large quantity of computer CPU time can be saved which is of great significance in the analysis of laminate with large layer numbers.

CONCLUSION REMARKS

Form the discussion on the element quality and the numerical results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. It is possible to use mixed finite element method for the analysis of interlaminar stresses.
2. The displacement element proposed in this paper is valid for the laminate bending problem including transverse shear effect.
3. The present hybrid stress element has coordinate invariance and correct rank, and is effective to analyse the interlaminar stress in composite laminate.

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Fig.1 Element illustration

Fig.2 Cylindrical bending problem

Fig. 3 Element convergence

Fig. 4 Distribution of σ_z along $Z=0$ calculated by using the hybrid stress model

Fig. 5 Distribution of σ_z along $Z=0$ calculated by using the mixed model

Fig. 6 Distribution of σ_z along $Z=h_0$ calculated by using the mixed model